

IMPACT OF FUEL SUBSIDY REMOVAL ON THE WELL-BEING OF STUDENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the well-being of students at the University of Calabar, focusing on transportation costs, mobility patterns, daily living expenses, and academic expenditures. The research was grounded in structural functionalism theory and employed a structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale to collect data from a sample of 164 students from the Faculty of Social Sciences, selected using Taro Yamane's formula. The data was analyzed using simple percentage and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The findings revealed that the removal of fuel subsidies significantly burdened students with increased transportation costs, prompting changes in their transportation modes. Furthermore, correlation analyses showed concerning trade-offs between essential expenses, highlighting the subsidy removal's implications for students' well-being. To mitigate these effects, the study recommends introducing targeted support programs, such as subsidized transportation schemes or educational grants, to alleviate the adverse impacts on academic

activities and overall well-being. The University of Calabar management should establish campus-specific subsidies, such as discounted meal plans, affordable hostel accommodations, and bursary programs. These measures would help cushion the effect of the high cost of living on students.

Keywords: *Fuel, Subsidy Removal, Transportation cost, Well-being, Student, University of Calabar*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria has been a contentious issue, with far-reaching consequences for the economy, citizens, and students. Initially introduced to alleviate poverty and stimulate economic activity, fuel subsidies had become a significant financial burden on the government, leading to recurrent budget deficits and limiting investments in critical sectors (Evans et al., 2023; Ohonba & Ogbeide, 2023). The Nigerian government's decision to remove fuel subsidies in 2021 aimed to free up public resources for developmental areas. However, this policy shift has led to a sharp increase in fuel prices, affecting the cost of living and transportation costs for students (Bagdatli & Ipek, 2022).

Students at the University of Calabar are facing numerous challenges, including higher transportation costs, reduced participation in extracurricular activities, and limited access to essential resources. The increasing cost of living is placing additional financial pressure on students, causing stress that adversely impacts their mental health and academic performance. Many students rely on public transportation due to the high cost of private vehicle ownership, making the increase in transportation costs particularly significant. Furthermore, the rise in fuel prices has exacerbated financial pressures on students, who often operate on tight budgets (Nwachukwu & Tumba, 2023).

The removal of fuel subsidies has also raised concerns about the potential impact on the economy and citizens. According to Yunusa et al. (2023), the removal of subsidies on Premium Motor Spirit is anticipated to result in a temporary increase in inflation. The World Bank predicts that a one-time adjustment will lead to higher inflation rates in 2023 and 2024 before they begin to decline and also predict that the removal of petrol subsidies will cause an increase in pump prices, resulting in immediate hikes in transportation costs. The indirect effects may lead to rising rental rates and increased prices for goods and services.

The potential benefits of removing subsidies seem to significantly outweigh the current challenges (Jesuola 2024). The substantial savings gained from this action could be strategically invested in critical sectors such as education, technology, infrastructure development, and the provision of subsidized agricultural inputs. Nevertheless, the government's failure to extend palliatives to students has raised concerns about the well-being of the average person in light of this subsidy removal. This situation has prompted a study on the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the well-being of students at the University of Calabar. The study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the impacts, offering insights that can inform policy decisions and institutional responses to better support students during this challenging period.

The study investigated the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the well-being of students of the University of Calabar. Specific objectives include: to assess how the removal of fuel subsidy has affected transportation cost and mobility patterns of students of University of Calabar; to examine the impact of fuel subsidy removal on university of Calabar daily living spending and Academic-expenditures.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual review

Fuel subsidy and removal

Fuel subsidies are mechanisms employed by governments to stabilize fuel prices, reduce the cost of living, and shield vulnerable populations from economic volatility. Ohonba and Ogbeide (2023) and Alade (2024), in separate studies state that in Nigeria, subsidy on PMS has been a significant aspect of fiscal policy, introduced in the 1970s as a response to oil price shocks. Over the years, this subsidy has grown unsustainable, consuming billions of naira annually, leading policymakers to argue for their removal as a necessary step toward economic reform. However, Evans *et al.*, (2023), posit that subsidy removal is often controversial because of its direct impact on fuel prices and the broader economy. For instance, studies from Indonesia and Ghana reveal that while subsidy removal can free up government funds for infrastructure and education, it also triggers inflation, particularly in transportation and food costs. In Nigeria, the removal of fuel subsidy in 2023 was met with widespread protests and highlighted the country's dependency on subsidized fuel for economic stability. Eden *et al.*, (2024) note that this underscores the need to evaluate the nuanced impact of such policies on specific demographics, such as university students.

In the Nigerian higher education system, students are particularly sensitive to economic shocks due to pre-existing financial constraints. For instance, at the University of Calabar, anecdotal evidence points to increased transportation costs as a significant barrier to consistent attendance, with many students opting to stay off-campus due to high commuting costs. Hostels on-campus, though cheaper, are often insufficient to accommodate the growing student population, leaving many to seek expensive off-campus alternatives. In similar institutions, such as the University of Ibadan, research has highlighted adaptive strategies employed by students, including carpooling, bulk food purchases, and informal employment. However, these coping mechanisms often come at the cost of reduced academic focus and time. By studying these patterns, we can better understand how students at the University of Calabar navigate the challenges brought on by subsidy removal.

The table below shows the history of subsidy removal in Nigeria. It x-rays the various petrol-adjustments in Nigeria since 2000.

Table 1

Historical trends of changes in fuel prices in Nigeria across different administrations (2000-2024)

S/N	Date	Administration	Price	Percentage change
1	2000	Obasanjo	N20.00	-
2	2000	Obasanjo	N22.00	10%
3	2001	Obasanjo	N26.00	18%
4	2003	Obasanjo	N40.00	54%
5	2004	Obasanjo	N45.00	13%
6	2007	Obasanjo	N70.00	56%
7	2007	Yar'Adua	N56.00	0.0%
8	2010-2012	Jonathan	N65.00	-
9	2012-2015	Jonathan	N141.00	117%

10	2016	Buhari	N145.00	
11	2020	Buhari	162.00	12%
12	2021	Buhari	165.00	2%
13	2023	Tinubu	500.00	203%
14	2024	Tinubu	1,100.00	120%

Source: Elekwachiet *al.*, 2024

Table 1 presented the historical trajectory of fuel price adjustments in Nigeria, reflecting successive policy decisions aimed at reducing or completely removing fuel subsidies. Beginning in 2000, successive administrations grappled with the challenge of balancing the anticipated macroeconomic gains of subsidy removal against its associated social and economic costs. Over time, these adjustments intensified, culminating in a major policy shift in 2023 under the Tinubu administration, when petrol prices increased sharply from ₦165 to ₦500 per litre following the full removal of fuel subsidy, representing an approximate 203 per cent increase. In 2024, fuel prices rose further to ₦617 per litre, resulting in a cumulative adjustment with far-reaching implications for inflation, transportation costs, and overall household expenditures.

For students of the University of Calabar, these sustained fuel price increases had particularly profound consequences. Rising transportation costs disproportionately affected students residing off campus, increasing the financial burden of daily commuting and, in some cases, contributing to higher rates of absenteeism. In addition, the general rise in the prices of goods and services eroded students' disposable income, compelling many to reduce spending on essential academic materials or engage in part-time employment to cope with rising living costs. These adjustments often came at the expense of academic concentration, health, and overall well-being.

This historical perspective underscored the necessity for targeted interventions to mitigate the adverse effects of fuel subsidy removal, especially for vulnerable groups such as students. It also highlighted the importance of situating subsidy reform policies within a broader socio-economic framework to ensure that policy outcomes remain equitable and do not undermine access to education or human capital development.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This study was anchored in the framework of structural functionalism, a sociological perspective whose intellectual roots can be traced to early classical theorists such as Auguste Comte, Herbert Spencer, and Émile Durkheim. Central to structural functionalism is the organismic analogy, which conceptualizes society as a cohesive system composed of interdependent parts that function together to sustain social order and stability.

Structural functionalism focuses on the major social structures and institutions within society and examines how their interactions contribute to the survival and continuity of the social system. Durkheim, a seminal figure in the development of this theory, advanced several foundational assumptions for understanding social life. He viewed society as an entity that exists independently of its individual members, with each component performing specific functions necessary for the maintenance of the whole. According to this perspective, the fulfillment of basic societal needs is essential for preventing abnormal or pathological states, as societies naturally tend toward equilibrium under conditions of normal functioning.

Durkheim further emphasized that the explanation of any social phenomenon requires the identification of both its efficient cause; the factor that produces it; and its function, defined as the contribution the phenomenon makes to the maintenance or continuity of the social system. In this regard, the function of a social fact is inherently social and must be understood in relation to the broader goals or needs of society.

Martindale (1965) expanded this conceptualization by defining function as any activity that shapes and sustains a system, encompassing both positive and negative consequences of social institutions and processes. Similarly, Marion (1952) conceptualized function as the condition or state that results from the continuous operation of a structure over time. He introduced the concepts of eufunction, outcomes that promote system stability and continuity, and dysfunction, which refers to adverse effects that undermine system performance and may lead to social breakdown.

Within the context of the Nigerian political and economic system, structural functionalism is particularly relevant. Various institutional structures have been established to deliver essential services to citizens at affordable rates (Okpa et al., 2020). Although political structures are diverse and often specialized, each is expected to perform designated functions that contribute to societal stability. The theory assumes that society exists as an autonomous entity distinct from its constituent parts, that each social component fulfills specific needs of the whole, and that societies tend toward equilibrium for normal functioning.

However, in practice, key institutions such as the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) and the Ministry of Petroleum Resources, often under the direct oversight of the President; have struggled to effectively maintain existing refineries or establish new ones. This institutional failure represents a structural dysfunction that has contributed to the removal of fuel subsidies, thereby triggering increases in transportation costs and the general cost of living, particularly in urban centers such as the Calabar Metropolis.

Despite its analytical strengths, structural functionalism has been criticized, particularly for its methodological tendency to identify functions first and then fit structures to those functions, sometimes resulting in empirical distortions. Critics have also argued that the theory inadequately accounts for social change and individual agency. Nevertheless, these limitations often reflect shortcomings in empirical application rather than inherent flaws in the theoretical framework itself.

Overall, structural functionalism provides a useful lens for examining the relationship between government policy, institutional performance, and social welfare. In this study, the framework facilitated an analysis of how dysfunctions in petroleum management institutions, such as the NNPC and the Ministry of Petroleum Resources, generated broader societal consequences, especially for students of the University of Calabar. Specifically, it helped explain how policy failures translated into increased transportation costs and living expenses, thereby adversely affecting student well-being and educational sustainability.

2.3 Empirical literature

A substantial body of recent research has examined the socio-economic and welfare impacts of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria, employing diverse methodologies and covering multiple sectors of the economy.

Akinola et al. (2024) investigated the long-run equilibrium effects of fossil fuel subsidy removal, exchange rate, and inflation on economic welfare in Nigeria using a Vector Error Correction

Model (VECM) with data spanning 1992 to 2023. The study found that, in the short run, fossil fuel subsidy removal and inflation had negative but statistically insignificant effects on economic welfare, while exchange rate exhibited a positive insignificant effect. In the long run, however, subsidy removal and inflation negatively and significantly influenced economic welfare, whereas the exchange rate positively and significantly affected economic welfare.

Obasi et al. (2024) examined the impact of fuel subsidy removal on food prices and consumer purchasing behavior in Abia State, focusing on civil servants, lecturers, students, transporters, businesspeople, farmers, and self-employed individuals in Umuahia and Aba. Using a combination of primary and secondary data, a sample of 196 respondents was selected based on Topman's formula. Data analysis employed Ordinal Least Squares (OLS) via SPSS version 23.0. The study revealed that fuel subsidy removal had a significant and positive effect on food prices, food purchases, and overall consumer purchase behavior in the state.

Meludu et al. (2024) analyzed the influence of subsidy removal on the prices of key food items in Southeastern Nigeria. Data from the National Bureau of Statistics were analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-tests, with results presented in histograms and bar charts. Findings indicated that prices of rice, beans, yam, garri, and tomatoes increased significantly after subsidy removal at the 10% significance level, while palm oil prices rose significantly at the 5% level. The study highlighted a rapid escalation in food prices and other commodities within a short period following subsidy removal.

Abang et al. (2024) employed time-series and machine learning techniques to examine the combined effects of fuel subsidy removal and insecurity on food inflation in Nigeria between 1984 and 2023. The study developed a predictive model to assess the impact of fuel subsidy removal on food inflation while controlling for insecurity. Results indicated that subsidy removal significantly increased food inflation, with insecurity exacerbating the effect. Specifically, a 10% increase in fuel prices was projected to raise food inflation by 5.6%, with insecurity contributing an additional 2.3% increase.

Fyneroad (2024) investigated whether the removal of petrol subsidies by the Federal Government violated the economic and welfare rights of Nigerians, including the right to livelihood. Using a doctrinal research methodology, the study concluded that the removal of petrol subsidies infringed upon the economic and welfare rights of citizens.

Onwuaro et al. (2024) assessed the impact of fuel subsidy removal on maize production in Kashere Ward, Akko Local Government Area, Gombe State. Data were collected from 294 farmers using structured questionnaires and analyzed through descriptive statistics and t-tests. The study found that subsidy removal significantly disrupted key farming activities, including purchasing inputs (54.08%), transportation (96.26%), labor hiring (88.10%), and profits from sales (86.05%). The t-test results were statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.0000$), indicating a strong negative effect on maize output.

Ajuzie (2024) explored the adverse effects of fuel subsidy removal on food insecurity and household living standards through an exploratory qualitative approach. The study highlighted that rising commodity prices, reduced disposable income, and limited access to essential goods have intensified hunger and economic instability, particularly for low-income families, thereby deepening household poverty.

Ali et al. (2024) conducted an empirical study on the socio-economic effects of fuel subsidy removal on household living standards in Adamawa State. Covering six local government areas across three senatorial zones, the study surveyed 400 respondents. Findings indicated that the majority of households experienced moderate reductions in disposable income and adjustments in expenditure patterns following subsidy removal, with business owners constituting the largest respondent group (73.25%). Descriptive statistics revealed slight declines in mean household income post-subsidy removal, highlighting the immediate socio-economic consequences on households.

Mohammed et al. (2020) investigated the impact of fuel subsidy removal on household socio-economic characteristics in Maiduguri, Borno State. Using survey data analyzed through descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis, the study found that household characteristics, including family size, number of dependents, and employment status, were significantly associated with the effects of fuel subsidy removal. The study recommended policy measures such as increased wages, family planning initiatives, and reduced transportation costs to alleviate the hardship faced by low-income earners.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate that fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria has wide-ranging socio-economic effects, influencing household income, food prices, agricultural productivity, consumer behavior, and overall welfare. The evidence underscores the critical need for targeted interventions to mitigate adverse impacts on vulnerable groups, including students, low-income families, and smallholder farmers.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a survey research design, which offers the advantage of collecting a large volume of data from a sizeable population in a cost-effective and efficient manner. The population of the study comprised 1,260 students from the Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Calabar. A sample of 165 students was selected, with the sample size determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) statistical formula. The study relied on primary data, collected through a structured questionnaire, which served as the main research instrument. The questionnaire was subjected to both face and content validity procedures to ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness.

To facilitate data analysis and improve comprehension, the collected data were presented using frequency distribution tables. Descriptive statistics, particularly simple percentage analysis, were employed to summarize responses and address research objectives. In testing hypotheses, the probability value (p-value) was used to assess the statistical significance of independent variables. Specifically, a p-value < 0.05 indicated that a variable was statistically significant, whereas a p-value > 0.05 suggested non-significance.

4.0 RESULTS PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, the data collected from the selected sample of small business owners were presented, analysed, and interpreted. A total of 165 questionnaires were distributed to respondents via an online survey. Analysis was conducted based on 156 valid and completed questionnaires, indicating that 9 questionnaires were not returned or were incomplete. The section focuses on analyzing data relevant to the research questions, providing insights into the study objectives.

4.1 Presentation of data relevant to the research questions

QuestionOne: How has the removal of fuel subsidy influenced transportation costs and mobility patterns among University of Calabar students?

Table 2

Transportation cost and mobility pattern Influences of removal of fuel subsidy among University of Calabar students

Changes	SA	A	N	D	SD	Frequencies	Percent
Increase in Transportation cost	96	34	10	10	6	156	94.5
Increase in time spent on Road	33	26	43	30	24	156	94.5
Changes in transportation mode	30	42	24	20	40	156	94.5
Reduction in school attendance	27	5	50	34	40	156	94.5
Combining trips to school	22	14	29	58	33	156	94.5

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 presented the significant effects of fuel subsidy removal on transportation patterns and student mobility at the University of Calabar. Notably, the increase in transportation costs elicited the strongest response among respondents. A total of 99 students strongly agreed and 35 agreed, representing 81.7% of the respondents, that transportation costs had increased considerably. This finding indicated that rising transportation expenses constituted the most immediate and widely experienced impact of subsidy removal on students.

Responses regarding time spent commuting were more varied. Overall, 59 students (36%) agreed or strongly agreed that they spent more time commuting to and from the university. However, a substantial neutral response from 47 students suggested that changes in commuting time were not solely attributable to fuel price increases but may also have been influenced by other factors such as route adjustments, traffic conditions, or the availability of alternative transportation options.

With respect to changes in modes of transportation, responses were polarized. While 72 students (44%) reported changing their mode of transport following the subsidy removal, 61 students (37%) disagreed or strongly disagreed. This pattern implied that although a significant proportion of students adapted by seeking alternative means of transportation, many continued to rely on their original modes despite higher costs.

Concerning school attendance, only 26 students (16%) reported a decline in attendance, whereas 73 students (44.5%) disagreed or strongly disagreed with the notion that their attendance had decreased. This trend suggested that most students prioritized academic participation despite increased transportation expenses, possibly by making financial or personal sacrifices in other areas.

Finally, the strategy of combining trips to school recorded limited adoption. Only 36 students (22%) agreed or strongly agreed that they combined trips, while 90 students (55%) disagreed or strongly disagreed. This outcome suggested that students faced constraints such as rigid academic schedules or logistical challenges that limited the practicality of trip consolidation.

Table 3
ANOVA results

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between Groups	18.324	4	4.581	2.825	0.027
Within Groups	243.250	150	1.622		
Total	261.574	154			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Results

Table 3 presented the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), which was conducted to determine whether the observed results were statistically significant and not attributable to random or statistical errors. The criterion for statistical significance required the significance value (p-value) to be less than 0.05. Based on the results reported in the table, the computed significance value was 0.027, which was below the 0.05 threshold. This result indicated that the model was statistically significant and that the observed variations were not generated by statistical errors.

Question Two: Impact of Fuel Subsidy Removal on University of Calabar Students' Daily Living Expenses and Academic-Related Spending

The results of the paired samples test revealed statistically significant relationships among key variables affected by the removal of fuel subsidies on students of the University of Calabar. The first comparison examined transportation costs in relation to changes in transportation modes. The findings showed a positive mean difference of 1.427, with a t-value of 9.107 and a significance level of $p < 0.001$. This strong positive and statistically significant result indicated that increases in transportation costs significantly influenced students' decisions to alter their modes of transportation. This finding demonstrated the direct effect of fuel subsidy removal on students' mobility and commuting behavior.

The second comparison assessed the relationship between food expenditures and accommodation costs. The results indicated a negative mean difference of -1.584, with a t-value of -11.655 and a significance level of $p < 0.001$. This statistically significant negative relationship suggested that rising accommodation costs were associated with adjustments in students' food expenditures, implying that students reallocated limited financial resources in response to increased living costs following fuel subsidy removal.

Table 4

Paired samples test analysis of transportation and living cost changes following fuel subsidy removal

Variable pairs	Mean	SD	SE	t-value	df	p-value
Transportation cost and mode changes	1.427	2.006	0.157	9.107	163	0.000
Food purchases and hostel accommodation cost	-1.584	1.687	0.136	-11.655	153	0.000

Source: Field Survey, 2025

This pronounced negative relationship indicated that students faced a clear trade-off between food expenditures and accommodation costs. Specifically, as accommodation costs increased, students' ability to maintain their usual food purchasing patterns declined significantly. Both relationships were statistically significant at the 1 per cent level ($p < 0.001$), with relatively low standard errors of 0.157 and 0.136, respectively, indicating a high level of precision in the estimated coefficients. Furthermore, the relatively high degrees of freedom ($df = 163$ and 153) and strong t-statistics provided robust statistical evidence of the impact of fuel subsidy removal on students' fundamental expenditure patterns, particularly in relation to essential needs such as transportation, food, and accommodation.

4.2 Discussion of findings

The study examined the significant impacts of fuel subsidy removal on students of the University of Calabar, and the findings were consistent with recent empirical research on fuel subsidy reforms in developing economies. The results revealed substantial effects on students' transportation behavior and overall living expenses. Specifically, the findings indicated that 81.7 per cent of the students experienced an increase in transportation costs. This high proportion highlighted a strong and direct relationship between fuel subsidy removal and increased transportation burdens, which potentially constrained access to education. This outcome aligned with existing evidence from other developing countries, where subsidy reforms have been shown to disproportionately affect low-income and student populations (Mohammed & Ibrahim, 2024).

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results further confirmed the statistical significance of changes in students' transportation patterns, with a p-value of 0.027. Despite the pronounced rise in transportation costs, only 16 per cent of the respondents reported a reduction in class attendance. This finding suggested a strong commitment to academic engagement among students, even in the face of heightened financial pressure. It also reflected the resilience of students who continued to prioritize educational participation despite adverse economic conditions.

Additionally, the paired samples test revealed critical relationships among key expenditure variables. The positive and statistically significant relationship between transportation costs and changes in transportation modes (mean = 1.427, $p < 0.001$) indicated that students adopted various adaptive strategies, such as altering commuting patterns or selecting more cost-efficient transport options. Conversely, the negative and significant relationship between food expenditure and

accommodation costs (mean = -1.584 , $p < 0.001$) revealed the existence of trade-offs that adversely affected students' basic living standards.

Importantly, the findings demonstrated a consistent pattern in which students prioritized academic attendance over other essential needs. This prioritization often occurred at the expense of food quality and accommodation conditions, underscoring the hidden welfare costs associated with fuel subsidy removal. These results emphasized the urgent need for targeted intervention measures, such as transportation subsidies, campus housing support, or student welfare schemes, to mitigate the adverse effects of fuel subsidy removal while ensuring sustained access to higher education.

5.0 Conclusion

The findings of this study clearly demonstrated that the removal of the fuel subsidy had significant and far-reaching implications for the welfare of students at the University of Calabar. The evidence showed that the policy negatively affected students' overall well-being by increasing the cost of essential items, particularly transportation, food, and accommodation. Correlation analyses revealed that students were compelled to make difficult trade-offs among these basic needs in an effort to cope with rising living expenses. Although such adaptive responses reflected students' strong commitment to their academic pursuits, they raised serious concerns regarding long-term welfare, academic sustainability, and quality of life.

The study further highlighted that continued exposure to these financial pressures could undermine students' health, learning outcomes, and overall academic performance. Consequently, the findings underscored the need for deliberate and well-targeted policy responses to ensure that broader economic reforms, such as fuel subsidy removal, do not unintentionally compromise access to higher education or the well-being of students.

5.1 Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following policy recommendations were proposed:

1. **Government Intervention:** The government should periodically reassess the fuel subsidy removal policy with a view to balancing national economic objectives and the welfare of vulnerable groups, particularly students. The introduction of targeted student support mechanisms, such as subsidized transportation schemes, education grants, or transport vouchers, would help mitigate the adverse effects of rising fuel and transportation costs on academic participation and student welfare.
2. **Institutional and Local Government Collaboration:** Universities, in collaboration with state and local governments, should develop affordable and reliable transportation alternatives for students. Initiatives such as university-operated shuttle bus systems or partnerships with private transport providers could significantly reduce commuting costs and ease the financial burden on students.
3. **University-Level Welfare Support:** The University of Calabar should consider implementing campus-specific support measures, including discounted meal plans, affordable hostel accommodation, and expanded bursary or hardship support programs. These interventions would help cushion the effects of the rising cost of living and enhance students' ability to sustain their academic and personal well-being.

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APPENDICES

SPSS RESULTS

		Statistics				
		Increased transp	Increase in time spend on road	Change of transportation mode	Reduction in school attendance	combining trips to school
N	Valid	164	164	164	154	155
	Missing	3	3	3	13	12

Frequency Table

		Increased transp			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	4.2	4.3	4.3
	disagree	12	7.2	7.3	11.6
	Neutral	11	6.6	6.7	18.3
	Agree	35	21.0	21.3	39.6
	Strongly Agree	99	59.3	60.4	100.0
	Total		164	98.2	100.0
Missing	System	3	1.8		
Total		167	100.0		

		Increase in time spend on road			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	27	16.2	16.5	16.5
	disagree	31	18.6	18.9	35.4
	Neutral	47	28.1	28.7	64.0
	Agree	26	15.6	15.9	79.9
	Strongly Agree	33	19.8	20.1	100.0
	Total		164	98.2	100.0
Missing	System	3	1.8		
Total		167	100.0		

Change of transportation mode

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	.00	9	5.4	5.5	5.5
	Strongly disagree	41	24.6	25.0	30.5
	disagree	20	12.0	12.2	42.7
	Neutral	22	13.2	13.4	56.1
	Agree	42	25.1	25.6	81.7
	Strongly Agree	30	18.0	18.3	100.0
	Total	164	98.2	100.0	
Missing	System	3	1.8		
Total		167	100.0		

Reduction in school attendance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	.00	6	3.6	3.9	3.9
	Strongly disagree	40	24.0	26.0	29.9
	disagree	33	19.8	21.4	51.3
	Neutral	49	29.3	31.8	83.1
	Agree	1	.6	.6	83.8
	Strongly Agree	25	15.0	16.2	100.0
	Total	154	92.2	100.0	
Missing	System	13	7.8		
Total		167	100.0		

combining trips to school

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	32	19.2	20.6	20.6
	disagree	58	34.7	37.4	58.1
	Neutral	29	17.4	18.7	76.8
	Agree	14	8.4	9.0	85.8
	Strongly Agree	22	13.2	14.2	100.0
	Total	155	92.8	100.0	
Missing	System	12	7.2		
Total		167	100.0		

REGRESSION

/MISSING LISTWISE
 /STATISTICS COEFF OUTS R ANOVA
 /CRITERIA=PIN(.05) POUT(.10)
 /NOORIGIN
 /DEPENDENT InceasrTP
 /METHOD=ENTER TimeConsumingChangeofTmodeReducedAttendanceTripcombination.

ANOVA

combining trips to school

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18.324	4	4.581	2.825	.027
Within Groups	243.250	150	1.622		
Total	261.574	154			

T-TEST PAIRS=InceasrTPDecreaseinfoodbudget WITH
 ChangeofTmodeIncreasedincostofaccomodation
 (PAIRED)
 /CRITERIA=CI(.9500)
 /MISSING=ANALYSIS.

T-Test

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Increased transp	4.2622	164	1.13431	.08857
	Change of transportation mode	2.8354	164	1.61008	.12573
Pair 2	reduction in food purchases	2.2078	154	.88322	.07117
	increased in cost of accommodation	3.7922	154	1.37995	.11120

Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Increased transp& Change of transportation mode	164	-.040	.611
Pair 2	reduction in food purchases & increased in cost of accommodation	154	-.066	.414

Q1		Paired Samples Test					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Paired Differences							
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
			Lower	Upper					
Pair 1	Increased transp - Change of transportation mode	1.42683	2.00631	.15667	1.11747	1.73619	9.107	163	.000
Pair 2	reduction in food purchases - increased in cost of accommodation	-1.58442	1.68694	.13594	-1.85297	1.31586	11.655	153	.000